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A RETROSPECTIVE ANALYSIS OF DENTOALVEOLAR ANOMALIES AT SCHOOL AGED CHILDREN

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A high prevalence of the dentoalveolar anomalies (DAA) and dental caries accompanying them complications define relevance and significance of the problem of early detection and prevention of these types of pathology [Adamchik AA., 2000; Arutyunov SD., 2006]. There is enough evidence to conclude that negligible short and long-term spontaneous dentoalveolar changes tend to occur in the mandibular dental arch after slow or rapid maxillary expansion or in the mixed and early permanent dentitions or after traumatic dental injuries [Alves AC de M., Maranhao OBV., Janson G., Garib DG., 2017; Kurt A. et al., 2019]. There is enough literature which approved of the dental anomalies as a multifactorial pathology [Caltabiano M., Verzi P., Scire Scappuzzo G., 2009; Little RM., 2012; Splieth C.H., 2004; Rohilla M., 2017; Roslan AA., Rahman NA., Alam MK.; 2018;].

OBJECTIVE: This study was carried to study the prevalence of dental anomalies at children aged 6-9 years, living in Bukhara region.

MATERIAL AND METHODS: there has been carried out a comparative retrospective analysis of 831 cases histories of patients with various occlusion abnormalities (dislocation, vertical incisive dioccluses or deep incisive occlusion) which admitted to out-patient treatment in regional dental clinic in Bukhara for 2005-2015 years. A P value of <0.05 is considered as significant. The confidence interval at 95% was set.

RESULTS: As the study results were established that from 831 children with orofacial dysfunctions, 39,1% of the children had a neutral occlusion in sagittal plane. Distal occlusion was diagnosed at 391 children, which accounted for 47,1% of all children with orofacial dysfunctions. At 115 (13,8%) patients, mesial occlusion was diagnosed.

It was revealed disorders at 86,2% of the children as an incisal disocclusion in 23,0% cases and deep incisal disocclusion in 43,2% cases in the vertical plane. It was to be noted that children with horizontal plane disorders were excluded from the study group and were admitted to treatment to the orthodontist.

We were found that in the age of 6-7 years in 66,5% cases children have had orofacial dysfunctions without signs of dental anomalies and deformities, in 16,5% of cases, dental anomalies and deformities together with orofacial dysfunctions were detected. Number of children without orofacial dysfunctions (OFD) and DAA accounted for 17,0%.

In children aged 8-9 years was revealed the following prevalence structure of DAA and OFD: children with DAA and OFD - 72,6%, children with OFD without DAA signs - 8,4%, children without OFD and DAA - 18,9%.

With age in the period of early replaceable occlusion, the number of children without OFD and DAA remains almost unchanged ($p > 0,10$), whereas a share of children with dentofacial anomalies and deformities were increased from 16,5% to 72,6% ($p < 0.001$), and children with orofacial dysfunctions without of DAA signs — reduced from 66,5% to 8,4% ($p < 0.001$).

CONCLUSIONS: orofacial dysfunctions have a high prevalence during the period of primary occlusal changes. With age, as they grow older, children with orofacial dysfunctions acquire dentoalveolar anomalies associated with functional impairment of MFA, which confirms the literary data about orofacial dysfunctions as “premorbid” states of DAA at children. More randomized studies with appropriate control group are required to better evaluate this issue.